

requires: N, 12.16; S, 9.26%; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 200 (NH), 1 520 (C=N), 1 030 and 1 240 (=C-O-C) and 650 cm^{-1} (C-S-C); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.6-1.7 (3H, d, CH_3), 2.1 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.4 (1H, s, NH), 5.5-5.7 (1H, q, CH) and 6.8-7.6 (8H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds (3b-1) were prepared (Table 1).

3- α -(2',4'-Dimethylphenoxy)ethyl-4-p-methoxyphenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (4f): A mixture of α -(2',4'-dimethylphenoxy)propionyl hydrazine (2.08 g, 0.01 mol) and *p*-methoxyphenyl isothiocyanate (1.65 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in sodium hydroxide solution (8%; 20 ml) for 5 h, then cooled, poured into large excess of water, stirred and filtered. The filtrate on acidification yielded a solid which was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aqueous alcohol, (82.3%), m.p. 172° (Found: N, 11.92; S, 8.87. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires: N, 11.83; S, 9.01%; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 120 (NH), 2 700 (SH), 1 520 (C=N), 1 010 and 1 240 (=C-O-C) and 1 070 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.4-1.5 (3H, d, CH_3), 1.9 (3H, s, *p*- CH_3), 2.1 (3H, s, *o*- CH_3), 3.2 (1H, s, SH), 3.7 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.0-5.2 (1H, q, CH) and 6.3-7.1 (7H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds (4a-e, g-1) were prepared (Table 1).

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Synthesis of some New Phenothiazine Derivatives

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PHENOTHIAZINE and its derivatives possess various biological activities¹. As a part of our research programme, we report the synthesis of some new *N*-substituted tricyclic hydrazides, thiosemicarbazides and five-membered heterocycles.

The key intermediates, *N*-substituted phenothiazine thiosemicarbazides were prepared by the reaction of appropriate ethyl/chloroformate, ethyl chloroacetate, ethyl bromopropionate and diethyl bromomalonate with phenothiazine in dry acetone in presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 followed by the reaction with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol to form the corresponding hydrazides (2a-d). These hydrazides (2) on refluxing with phenyl isothiocyanate in alcohol gave the corresponding N_{10} -substituted phenothiazine thiosemicarbazides (3a-d), which were further cyclised to the five-membered heterocyclic N_{10} -substituted phenothiazines (4-6; Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

***N*₁₀-Carboethoxyphenothiazine (1a)**: A mixture of phenothiazine (199 g, 0.1 mol), substituted haloester (10.85 g, 0.1 mol) in dry acetone (40 ml) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (2 g) was refluxed for 24 h, then cooled, filtered and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol to furnish 1a (23.0 g, 85%), m.p. 173° (Found: C, 66.38; H, 4.79; N, 5.14; S, 11.78. C₁₅H₁₂O₂NS calcd. for: C, 66.42; H, 4.79; N, 5.16; S, 11.80%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 710 (C=O ester) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 1.3 (3H, t, ester CH₃), 4.2 (2H, q, ester CH₂) and 6.9–7.5 (8H, m, ArH).

***N*₁₀-Hydrazidophenothiazine (2a)**: To a solution of 1a (2.71 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), hydrazine hydrate (0.5 g, 0.01 mol) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 2–3 h, then cooled. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to yield 2a (2.18 g, 85%), m.p. 171° (Found: C, 60.60; H, 4.20; N, 16.27. C₁₅H₁₁ON₂S calcd. for: C, 60.70, H, 4.28; N, 16.34%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 350 (NHNH₂) and 1 670 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 2.5 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.0–7.5 (8H, m, ArH) and 7.8 (1H, s, CONH).

4-Aryl-1-(*N*₁₀-phenothiazinoyl)thiosemicarbazide (3a): A mixture of 2a (0.257 g, 0.001 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.135 g, 0.001 mol) was refluxed in alcohol for 3–4 h, then cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol to furnish 3a (0.3 g, 75%), m.p. 152° (Found: C, 61.13, H, 4.01; N, 14.12. C₂₀H₁₆ON₂S₂ calcd. for: C, 61.22; H, 4.08; N, 14.28%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 350–3 400 (NH), 1 670 (CONH) and 1 325–1 354 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ 7.5–7.6 (13H, m, ArH) and 7.8 (1H, s br, NHCO exchangeable with D₂O).

4-Aryl-3-(*N*₁₀-phenothiazinyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (4a): Compound 3a (0.392 g, 0.001 mol) was refluxed with 2*N* NaOH (2 ml) for 3 h, then cooled and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with glacial acetic acid gave a solid which when recrystallised from ethanol gave 4a (0.3 g, 80%), m.p. 74° (Found: C, 64.13; H, 3.69; N, 14.92. C₂₀H₁₄N₄S₂ calcd. for: C, 64.17; H, 3.74; N, 14.97%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 250–3 300 (NH) and 1 600–1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 7–7.9 (13H, m, ArH) and 11.5–12.0 (1H, s, SH).

5-Arylamino-2-(*N*₁₀-phenothiazinyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (5a): To a mixture of 3a (0.392 g, 0.001 mol) in NaOH (4*N*; 4 ml) was added I₂ solution in KI till the colour of I₂ persisted. The reaction mixture was further concentrated for 4–5 h, then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to give 5a (0.25 g, 70%), m.p. 158° (Found: C, 67.01; H, 3.86; N, 15.59; S, 8.91. C₂₀H₁₄ON₄S calcd. for: C, 67.03; H, 3.91; N, 15.64; S, 8.93%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 150–3 250 (NH), 1 610–1 625 (C=N) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 6.7 (1H, s, NH) and 7–8 (13H, m, ArH).

5-Arylamino-2-(*N*₁₀-phenothiazinyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (6a): Compound 3a (0.392 g, 0.001 mol) was

dissolved in syrupy phosphoric acid (3 ml), heated at 120° for 50 min kept overnight and then poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised to give 6a (0.3 g, 80%), m.p. 59° (Found: C, 64.11, H, 3.71; N, 14.90; S, 17.08. C₂₀H₁₄N₄S₂ calcd. for: C, 64.17; H, 3.74; N, 14.97; S, 17.11%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 200–3 300 (NH), 1 600–1 625 (C=N); 700–720 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C); δ 6.7–6.8 (1H, s, NH) and 7.0–7.8 (13H, m, ArH).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF PHENOTHIAZINE ESTERS (1)^a, HYDRAZIDES (2)^a, THIOSEMICARBAZIDES (3)^a, TRIAZOLES (4)^a, OXADIAZOLES (5)^a AND THIADIAZOLES (6)^a

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
1b	80	205	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S
1c	75	159	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S
1d	75	156	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S
2b	80	189	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ON ₂ S
2c	85	181	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ ON ₂ S
2d	85	209	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S
3b	75	70	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S ₂
3c	70	158	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ ON ₂ S ₂
3d	80	175	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂
4b	85	67	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂
4c	75	160	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₄ S ₂
4d	75	66	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₄ S ₂
5b	75	161	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S
5c	70	150	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ON ₄ S
5d	80	155	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₄ S
6b	70	55	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂
6c	70	102	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₄ S ₂
6d	75	70	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₄ S ₂

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Phytochemical Investigation of *Pedilanthus tithymaloides* (L.) Poit.

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[N continuation of our previous works^{1,2} on triterpenoids of *Euphorbiaceae*, the chemical investigation of *Pedilanthus tithymaloides* Poit. (*Euphorbiaceae*)³ was undertaken. *P. tithymaloides* is a

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